

Genetic Evaluation and Utilization

DISEASE RESISTANCE

Evaluation of National Uniform Rice Yield Trial 1985 against bacterial blight (BB) in Pakistan

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BB incited by *Xanthomonas campestris* pv. *oryzae* (Ishiyama) Dye occurs in almost all provinces of Pakistan; it has caused considerable yield loss over the last 4 yr. We tested 19 rice cultivars for reaction to BB at 10 sites in different ecological zones under natural epiphytotic conditions in 1985.

Lines were planted in 4-m² plots at 20- × 15-cm spacing in a randomized block design with 4 replications.

Recommended agronomic practices were applied. Disease was measured according to the *Standard evaluation system for rice* (SES) 20 d before harvest.

Lateefy and IR161-1-1-1 showed the highest mean disease score, DM16-5-1 the lowest (see table). □

Response of rice cultivars to BB in Pakistan.

Cultivar	Score ^a	
Lateefy	6.20	h
IR161-1-1-1	6.20	h
DR83	5.80	gh
Swat II	5.80	gh
Swat I	5.40	fgh
Basmati 370-1	4.80	efgh
RGP135	4.80	efgh
DR82	4.60	defgh
KS282	3.80	cdefg
IR6	3.40	cdef
IR42	3.40	bcde
IR16461	3.20	bcde
IR8-5	2.60	abcd
IR2153-276	2.60	abcd
IR1529-ECIA	2.60	abcd
IR6-104	1.80	abc
Jajai 77-1	1.20	ab
Basmati 370	1.20	ab
DM16-5-1	1.00	a

^aBased on 1980 SES scale. 0-9: 0 = no incidence, 9 = 26-50% incidence. Each score is the average of 10 locations in different ecological zones of Pakistan. Means followed by the same letter are not significantly different at the 1% level by Duncan's multiple range test.

Resistance of rice germplasm to bacterial blight (BB) at Ludhiana, India

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We evaluated a germplasm collection of rices obtained from various places in India and internationally for resistance to BB caused by *Xanthomonas campestris* pv. *oryzae*. Each cultivar or line was planted in a 3-m row; standard agronomic practices were followed. At 70 d after sowing (DAS), each line was inoculated with isolate IXO-3, the most virulent of 11 isolates identified from the Punjab, using the standard clipping method. The inoculum consisted of 48-h-old growth of the bacterium, multiplied on PSA at 25 °C, at a

Mean lesion length and reaction of rice lines and cultivars to BB caused by *Xanthomonas campestris* pv. *oryzae*. Ludhiana, India.

Cultivar or line name	Mean lesion length (cm)	
	70 DAS	90 DAS
<i>R at 70 DAS and 90 DAS</i>		
Palman 579	1.9	2.6
NCS83	0.4	1.4
NCS84	0.4	1.6
TCA368	1.0	2.6
IR22	1.6	1.0
DZ78	1.8	1.8
IR46828-B	1.6	2.6
IR18350-93-2	1.6	2.6
IR21820-154-3-2-2-3	1.9	3.0
IR25587-133-3-2-2-2	1.0	1.6
IR25916-42-3-3-2-2	1.6	1.6
IR27325-63-2-2	1.6	1.6
IR29692-65-2-3	1.6	3.0
IR31803-32-2	1.9	3.0
IR42	1.6	3.0
IR46	1.6	3.0
IR4744-295-2-3	1.0	3.4
IR50	1.6	1.6
CR333-6-1 (Jagannath/Mahsuri)	1.6	3.0
B4032D-MR-1-3-1	1.0	1.6
IR15529-253-3-2-2-2	1.6	2.6
IR15529-256-1	1.0	2.6
IR15795-151-2-3-2-2	1.0	1.6
IR15797-74-1-3-2	1.6	1.6
IR25586-108-1-2-2-2	1.9	3.4

Table continued.

Cultivar or line name	Mean lesion length (cm)	
	70 DAS	90 DAS
IR27316-6-2-2	1.9	3.0
IR28154-101-3-2	1.6	3.4
IR2035-117-3	1.6	3.0
IR64	1.6	3.0
<i>R at 70 DAS and MR at 90 DAS</i>		
Amritsari HR 22	1.9	5.6
ARC5752	1.6	5.6
NCS16	1.6	4.4
ARC10486	1.9	5.6
TCA728	1.4	4.0
201-1-27	1.9	5.0
PR107	1.4	4.0
RP2068-32-2-3	1.9	5.0
RP1801-21-24-20-9	1.9	4.4
IR13475-7-3-2	1.6	4.4
HAU2-165-3-3	1.6	3.8
IR13525-43-2-3-1-3-2	1.6	4.0
IR15529-256-1	1.9	4.2
IR19728-9-3-2	1.9	6.8
IR25587-67-1-3-3-3	1.6	6.4
IR48	1.9	5.4
NCS211	1.6	5.0
CR333-6-2 (Jagannath/Mahsuri)	1.6	5.0
IR15527-21-2-3	1.6	5.0
IR18350-93-2	1.9	5.0
HKR26	1.6	5.0
HKR36	1.6	6.4
<i>MR at 70 DAS and R at 90 DAS</i>		
Nagkayat (HB62)	3.2	3.4
Nagra 41/14	2.2	2.6
IR46830	(B)2.8	2.8
CR333-1-1-3 (Jagannath/Mahsuri)	4.0	6.2
CR333-1-15-2 (Jagannath/Mahsuri)	3.0	3.4
RP1800-14-11-22-4	2.6	3.0
IR13240-82-2-3-2-3-1	3.4	2.0
IR13538-48-2-3-1	2.4	3.0
IR15429-268-1-2-1	3.0	3.4
IR17492-18-6-1-1-3-3	3.6	2.6
IR25588-7-3-1	3.6	2.2
IR25863-35-3-3	3.0	3.4
IR28125-79-3-3-2	2.4	3.0
IR28154-101-3-2	3.0	3.0
IR54	3.0	3.6
IR56	2.6	3.0
IR58	3.0	3.0
Bahbolon	3.2	2.4
IR17492-18-6-1-1-3-3	3.0	1.0
IR21820-154-3-2-2-3	2.6	3.0
IR25587-133-3-2-2-2	3.2	1.0
IR27325-27-3-3	3.4	3.0
IR29692-65-2-3	3.0	1.6
IR31803-32-2	2.6	1.0
IR32307-107-3-2-2	3.0	1.6
HKR30	2.6	1.6
IR13475-7-3-2	3.8	3.0
IR13458-117-2-3-2-3	2.4	3.0
Susceptible check TN1	7.6	14.6

concentration of 10^9 cells/ mi.

Lesion length was measured 14 d after inoculation. Rices with lesion lengths up to 25% of that observed on highly susceptible TN1 were classified resistant (R); those with lesion lengths 26-50% of that on TN1 were classified moderately

resistant (MR); the remaining lines were classified susceptible. The experiment was repeated at 90 DAS with lines classified R or MR in the first test.

Of 800 lines or cultivars screened, 29 were R at 70 and 90 DAS; 22 were R at 70 DAS and MR at 90 DAS; 28 were

MR at 70 DAS and R at 90 DAS (see table). Some sources of resistance detected here are being used in a crossing program for detailed genetic analysis of resistance to *X. campestris* pv. *oryzae*. □

Genetic Evaluation and Utilization INSECT RESISTANCE

Sources of resistance to rice thrips

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Severe thrips *Stenchaetothrips biformis* (Bagnall) damage kills rice varieties IR20, IR50, Vaigai, and Bhavani in the seedling stage. We observed differences in levels of resistance to thrips in the rice germplasm collections maintained at

Table 1. Sources of resistance to thrips *S. biformis* (Bagnall). TNAU, Coimbatore, India, 1986.

Country	Source	
	no.	Percentage
India	74	77.9
USA	5	5.3
France	6	6.3
Japan	4	4.2
China	2	2.1
Nigeria	1	1.0
Netherlands	1	1.0
Taiwan	1	1.0
USSR	1	1.0
Total	95	100

Table 2. Sources of resistance to thrips from India, 1986.

State	Source	
	no.	Percentage
Tamil Nadu	33	44.6
Kerala	12	16.2
Orissa	10	13.5
Assam	7	9.5
Karnataka	5	6.8
Bengal	3	4.0
Maharashtra	3	4.0
Andhra Pradesh	1	1.4
Total	74	100

Paddy Breeding Station, TNAU. Hence, we field-evaluated 1,840 traditional rice cultivars for thrips resistance during Oct 1986.

Seeds were sown in three 1-m-long rows at 1 seed/cm. Resistant Ptb 33 and susceptible TN1 checks were sown at random. TN1 seedlings were completely

killed at 20 d after seeding. Damage rating was based on *Standard evaluation system for rice* 0-9 scale.

This mass screening identified 95 resistance sources, more than 75% originating in India (Table 1), most of them from Kerala and Tamil Nadu (Table 2). □

Varietal resistance to rice hispa

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Rice hispa *Dicladispa armigera* Oliv. is becoming increasingly important in many Asian countries. Pest attack was severe in Madhubani, Darbhanga, and Samastipur districts of Bihar, India, during the 1983 and 1984 wet seasons (WS).

Ten elite lines were screened in iron trays covered with cages in Pusa in 1984 WS. The lines were randomized and

replicated three times. One hundred hispa adults, collected from the field, were released when the plants were 15 d old (4-leaf stage). Percentage of damaged leaves, number of eggs laid, number of grubs, and grub survival percentage were recorded on 10 plants taken randomly in each replication (see table).

Type 3, a scented rice variety from Uttar Pradesh, was least preferred by the insect. The resistance mechanism seems to be both nonpreference and antibiosis. Other lines including TCA4, IET6263, and Rajendra Shan 201 were highly susceptible. □

Screening of rice varieties against rice hispa in cages. Bihar, India, 1984 wet season.

Variety	Damaged leaves (%)	Eggs (no./plant)	Grubs (no./plant)	Grub survival (%)
Radha (BR4)	90.0	1.53	1.5	71.7
Saket 4	74.4	2.17	2.2	67.5
Type 3	59.7	0.70	0.7	62.1
Pankaj	70.1	1.50	2.4	70.9
Rajshree (TCA80-4)	84.6	2.06	2.1	73.9
IET6263	87.9	3.13	3.3	69.5
BR34	88.5	2.50	2.5	77.5
Rajendra Shan 201	93.9	2.80	2.8	69.7
TCA4	95.6	2.13	2.1	67.6
Sugandha	82.9	2.36	1.5	82.6
CD (0.05%)	4.2	0.50	0.6	4.0
CV (%)	3.7	14.19	16.2	4.1